

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT): PROBLEMS AND DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS

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Abstract

The article explains the essence of the term "Internet of Things". Various IoT solutions available today, their functionality, the technologies used and the development trends of this concept are analyzed. Also, the most current trends in the development of Internet of Things (IoT) information technologies, solutions developed in accordance with the concept of the Internet of Things are reviewed and analyzed. The main problems, ways and methods of solving this concept are investigated.

Keywords: IoT, RFID, wireless sensor network, IoT architecture, IoT concept, IoT applications, IoT security, IPv6, smart home, smart city, smart enterprise

Introduction.

In 1999, the Auto-ID Center, which deals with radio frequency identification (RFID) technologies and sensor technologies, was established at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. In the same year, the term "Internet of Things" (IoT) was used for the first time to express the network of objects connected to the Internet by the application of RFID (radio frequency identification) technologies by the Auto-ID laboratory of this center, and thus the concept of IoT was born. (Aliguliyev R.M., Mahmudov R.Sh., 2011)

IoT is a unified network in which a large number of objects are connected through communication and information infrastructure. They exchange information with each other and work in real time without human intervention. The ultimate goal of the Internet of Things is to create a better world for people when objects around them understand their wishes and therefore act without any explicit instructions. Moreover, the quality of management and control systems can be improved by using IoT technologies in various fields of science. Hashimov (2020) shows in his article that "The essence of the IoT concept is that the objects or things that surround us are provided with miniature identification and sensor (sensitive) devices and interact through wired and wireless connections (satellite, mobile connection, Wi-Fi and Bluetooth), communicates and ensures that the processes are performed completely automatically" (Hashimov M.A., 2020).

According to another definition, the "Internet of Things" refers to a globally distributed network (or networks) of physical objects capable of sensing or influencing their environment by interacting with each

other, other machines or computers. Such "smart" objects have a wide range of sizes and capacities - from household appliances, industrial robots, cars, trains to things that exist in the daily life of any person (watch, bracelet, shirt, etc.). (Roslyakov, A.V., 2015)

Today, it is possible to observe areas completely affected by the Internet of Things: Smart cities, environment, health, energy, transportation, public safety, etc. In this article, we will analyze the functionality of IoT solutions available in the modern world.

The purpose of the research: to analyze the problems and benefits of using the Internet of Things in various fields, to examine its development directions.

The main hypothesis of the study is that if the application of the Internet of Things takes place in all fields of activity, it will significantly change the livelihood and life of these people for the better.

Tasks of the study:

1. To analyze and study the researches and literature sources on this problem;
2. To analyze the pros and cons of the Internet of Things;
3. To analyze the directions of development of the Internet of Things in the future;

Research methods:

- 1) theoretical analysis of available materials on the Internet;
- 2) Comparison;
- 3) Sociological survey;

The importance. The importance of research for our region is the demand for the development of various technologies and the improvement of the quality of life at a modern level.

Tədqiqatın materialı və metodları.

In numerous literature and Internet sources, the Internet of Things phenomenon has been described by researchers with completely different models, ranging from technocratic models. For example, the Internet of Things is presented as an infrastructure network that uniquely connects defined physical and virtual objects, objects, and devices through telecommunications.

Nikola Tesla was talking about the IoT when he predicted that the radio would be a "brain center" for small gadgets that would fit in a pocket. And so it happened: the Internet connected all computers into a single network, and household appliances and devices became its tools. The peculiarity of IoT is that the system involves not only computers and phones, but also almost any everyday object equipped with built-in tools and technologies to interact with each other or with the external environment³.

Functionality of IoT solutions

The Internet of Things is sometimes interpreted as a synonym for smart systems: smart devices, smart homes, smart city, smart environment, smart enterprises, etc. Let's take a closer look at them.

Smart devices can collect data, track activities, and customize experiences for users' needs and desires. They can be worn on different parts of the body (head, eyes, wrists, waist, arms, fingers, feet) or these devices can be sewn into different items of clothing. (Papulovskaya N.V., 2022).

A smart home is the integration of technology and services through an Internet network of electronic devices in a home, built to improve the quality of people's lives. Solutions in this category make the life of homeowners more comfortable and enjoyable. Some of them are designed to help the elderly in daily activities and monitoring their health. Due to the high market potential, more and more smart home solutions are entering the market - smart energy and resource management is mainly focused on the interaction of the system and human activity (Shafaqatov R.Ş., 2021).

A smart city is an urban area with developed infrastructure, communication and favorable market. It is a city where information technology is central to providing basic services to residents. Many technology platforms exist, including automated sensor networks and data centers. In fact, urban IoT is focused on using state-of-the-art communication technologies to support additional services for city administration and citizens. The application of the IoT paradigm to the urban context is of particular interest, because it responds to the trend of many national governments in the direction of applying information and communication solutions in the management of public affairs (Shafaqatov R.Ş., 2021).

Smart environment in the city includes smart management of mobility, utilities, buildings. Services supported by the IoT paradigm in a smart city environment include health care facilities, waste management, air

quality, noise levels, congestion, parking, water quality, environmental conditions, etc. can control. For example, the Air Quality EGG device with a sensor system helps monitor air quality (Giuseppe Ruggeri, 2020).

A smart enterprise. Enterprise IoT solutions are designed to support infrastructure and more versatile functionality across industries. Modern enterprises already use several interfaces for smart elements, but in the future, with the increase in computing and communication capabilities of these elements, the boundaries between the production area and suppliers, consumers, workers and researchers, and between production and service may disappear. absolutely. Intelligent mechanisms for collecting, filtering, combining and transforming data can be deployed and operated at the edge of the network or, if necessary, within the network.

Smart environment in the city includes smart management of mobility, utilities, buildings. Services supported by the IoT paradigm in a smart city environment include health care facilities, waste management, air quality, noise levels, congestion, parking, water quality, environmental conditions, etc. can control. For example, the Air Quality EGG device with a sensor system helps monitor air quality (Giuseppe Ruggeri, 2020).

Currently, software is already a key driver in many industries, and the business models of the future will be largely based on IoT mechanisms. If we look at the concept of "Internet of things" more broadly, we will witness many other interesting areas for the application of its possibilities. The most promising are manufacturing, supply chain optimization, energy, healthcare, transportation and logistics. For example, the Irish company Wattics (Wattics, 2011) has developed innovative panels that allow energy consumption to be managed via the Internet. The device analyzes the rationality of electricity use and warns the user in case of excessive energy consumption. The development of the company Cantaloupe Systems from the United States (Cantaloupe Systems, 2012) allows the owners of vending machines to remotely monitor the stocks in them. Timely and optimal replenishment strategies are determined based on contextual information about usage patterns. Another American company - Engaugeinc (Gubbi J., 2013) - is the creator of smart sensors for remote monitoring of security equipment (for example, fire extinguishing systems), which lead to cost reduction and increased life safety. The company provides

Development problems of the Internet of things.

It seems to us that the necessary conditions - technological, social, legal, financial and business conditions - should be created for the widespread application of the Internet of Things. Only then will IoT be widely recognized in the world community. Let's consider some problems that hinder the development of IoT (Gryaznov C.A. 2021).

³ <https://proglib.io/p/top-10-aktualnyh-knig-po-tehnologiyam-interneta-veshchey-ot-novichka-do-professional-a-2021-09-11>

Standards and interoperability. Standards are important in creating markets for new technologies. If devices from different manufacturers use different standards, interoperability will be more difficult, additional gateways will be required to switch from one standard to another. In addition, a company that controls different parts of a vertical market (for example, acquiring data, integrating it with other data streams and using it to develop innovative solutions or provide services) can crowd out smaller players and entrepreneurs. The lack of uniform standards can also create obstacles for consumers, for example, when a device from one manufacturer is replaced by a similar device from another manufacturer, it is not possible to transfer accumulated data and users lose virtually no benefit. the data they collect over time.

Security and privacy. As the Internet of Things connects many different devices, the risk of introducing malware at decentralized access points increases. In this case, inexpensive devices located in physically compromised locations are most susceptible to interference.

With remote sensors and key use case monitoring for IoT, sensitivity increases for access and data ownership control. It's worth noting that the recent high-profile data security breach involving Target and Home Depot was made possible by stolen credentials from third-party vendors, allowing attackers to gain access to their payment systems.

Integration challenges. Integrating and testing IoT systems with multiple platforms, multiple protocols, and a large number of APIs is currently a challenge. The rapid development of APIs is likely to incur unforeseen costs on developers, which will negatively impact the ability of project teams to add new features.

Protocol wars and competing standards. The large number of players participating in IoT will inevitably clash with each other as they try to defend their system advantage. Currently, open system advocates are trying to set new standards. We see the actual creation of several standards evolving based on the various requirements dictated by the class of devices, capabilities, capabilities, and needs. This will allow platform vendors and third-party developers to influence future standards.

Specific use cases. Lack of clear use cases or examples showing profit/loss levels slows IoT development. Mass adoption of IoT will require sound, customer-oriented communication and “what's in it for me” messaging. IoT providers should be prepared to talk about the key benefits of their services and do so in as detailed, convincing and specific a way as possible.

Result. The potential of IoT is great, but the presence of problems hinders the development of the Internet of Things. In this article, we identified some of them. Obstacles to the development of the IT industry arise due to the excessive number of devices, insufficient communication between the physical and digital world, open systems and ongoing concerns about privacy and security. Every day, everyone involved in the Internet installation of Items will have to work on these tasks in the near future.

References

1. Aliguliyev R.M., Mahmudov R.Sh. The Internet of Things: Nature, Opportunities and Challenges. Information society problems, Hashimov M.A. Issues of using fog technology in the Internet of Things environment. Information technology issues, 2020, No. 2, 80–90
2. Shafaqatov R.Ş. Projection of the near future. Smart Azerbaijan concept. 2021// https://www.academia.edu/78051534/Smart_Azerbaijan_an_Smart_Azerbaijan_
3. Roslyakov, A.V. Internet of things: textbook [text] / A.V. Roslyakov, S.V. Vanyashin, A.Yu. Grebeshkov. - Samara: PSUTI, 2015. - 200 p.
4. Papulovskaya N.V. Fundamentals of the Internet of Things: a teaching aid / N.V. Papulovskaya; Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation.— Yekaterinburg: Ural Publishing House. un-ta, 2022. - 104 p.
5. Giuseppe Ruggeri, Valeria Loscri, Marica Amadeo, Carlos T. Calafate. The Internet of Things for Smart Environments.// https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339995993_The_Internet_of_Things_for_Smart_Environments. Published: 14 March 2020
6. Wattics. Smart metering, 2011. Электронный ресурс: URL: [http:// www.wattics.com/](http://www.wattics.com/)
7. Cantaloupe Systems. Seed Platform, 2012. Электронный ресурс: URL: <http://www.cantaloupesys.com/>
8. Gubbi J., Buyya R., Marusic S., Pal-aniswami M. Internet of Things (IoT): A Vision, Architectural Elements, and Future Directions // Future Generation Computer Systems. - 2013. - Vol. 29, Iss. 7. - P. 1645-1660.
9. Gryaznov S.A. Spectrum of the Internet of Things. // Journal of Economy and Business, vol. 4-1 (74), 2021., -126-128